

CHARACTERIZATION AND MODELING OF METASTABLE β -TITANIUM ALLOYS FOR BIOMEDICAL APPLICATIONS

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Abstract: Metastable β -titanium alloys feature great potential for use in biomedical applications, such as surgical instruments and biomimetic devices. Our study presents results from extensive experimental and theoretical research on the mechanical behavior of three specific metastable β -titanium systems, in which phase transformations play a key role. In particular, we address the adjustment of elastic properties by mechanical loading, the development of constitutive models to predict (thermo)mechanical response, and the design of product functionality through computational structural analysis. We also provide basic material science context and outline the envisaged application potential.

Keywords: metastable β -titanium alloys; shape memory; TWIP; elasticity; modeling; hip joint endoprosthesis

1 Introduction

The diversity of attainable mechanical properties makes so-called metastable β -titanium alloys particularly attractive for the development and design of applications across diverse industries, including aerospace or biomedical. By alloying the pure titanium with so-called β -stabilizing elements (e.g., Mo, V, Nb, or Ta), the body-centered cubic (bcc) β -phase can alter the original hexagonal close-packed (hcp) α -phase as the phase achieved by quenching to room temperature. However, the product alloys remain in a metastable state, which motivates their naming. By deliberate tailoring of their chemical composition and heat treatment, various initial phase compositions and microstructures can be achieved, which enables a rich palette of microstructural mechanisms to accommodate imposed deformation. Indeed, in addition to “conventional” dislocation slipping, stress-induced martensitic transformation from bcc β phase to a lower-symmetric phase, e.g., orthorhombic α' phase or hcp α' phase, stress-induced transformation to hexagonal ω phase, and deformation twinning can be employed to increase ductility, improve cold-workability, or adjust elastic properties of the material [1].

In this contribution, we present our experimental and theoretical investigation of the mechanical behavior of different β -titanium systems and, simultaneously, provide a broader context, including materials science background and motivation from prospective real-world applications. We focus on three case studies that address particular “families” of β -titanium alloys, each with a distinct research purpose and featuring distinct scientific challenges.

2 Adjusting the elastic properties of Ti-Mo alloys via deformation

Research on the Ti-Mo system dating back to the 2010s has increased interest in resolving the “strength–ductility trade-off” in metastable β -titanium alloys by involving more deformation mechanisms. Indeed, by controlling composition and processing, the interaction among slip, phase transformation, and deformation twinning allows achieving a superior combination of toughness and formability. So-called transformation-induced plasticity (TRIP) and twinning-induced plasticity (TWIP), i.e., the dynamic restriction of dislocation motion during deformation by various phase interfaces and twin boundaries, play the key role in this respect [2]. Theoretical and statistical investigation of the relation between chemical composition and occurrence of TRIP, TWIP, or their combination resulted in semi-empirical guidelines for the development of new metastable Ti-based binary, ternary, or quaternary alloys. For

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Figure 1: Evolution of true stress (full black line), work hardening rate (blue line), and Young’s modulus (red circles) of polycrystalline Ti-15Mo alloy subjected to tensile deformation up to approx. 34% true strain. The elastic modulus was determined for the undeformed state and after unloading from approx. 18% and 34% true strain in the loading direction. The dotted line marks the region of roughly constant hardening rate.

instance, a variation of just a few percent in molybdenum alters the dominant deformation mechanism, and hence the mechanical characteristics of the Ti-Mo system [1].

Recently, we have observed a dramatic variation of elastic properties induced by mechanical deformation in Ti-Mo alloys. Fig. 1 shows the tensile deformation of polycrystalline Ti-15Mo (wt.%) up to approx. 34% true strain (full black line) with subsequent unloading together with the corresponding strain hardening computed for the loading phase (blue line). The right axis shows the values of Young’s modulus measured in the loading direction, determined ex-situ at the undeformed state, after unloading from the maximum deformation, and after unloading from approx. 18% deformation (full circles). The elastic properties were determined using contactless resonant ultrasound spectroscopy, a characterization method that analyzes resonant frequencies and modes of small, freely vibrating samples after thermal excitation; see [3] for details.

For low strains, a significant decrease in the strain-hardening rate is observed. The strain hardening is rather steady for medium strains, i.e., between approx. 5% and 15% true deformation (see the dotted line as an eyeguide), and then it slowly declines. This evolution confirms previous findings [4] and indicates that the TWIP effect delivers high work hardening and large ductility in this type of alloy. The Young’s modulus shows a sharp decrease both after the first half of the loading phase, where the twinning activity ceases, and after unloading from the maximum tension. However, the deformation after approx. 17% strain is believed to be dominated by dislocation-mediated plasticity [4]. Hence, further microstructural characterization is needed to clarify the phenomena underlying the observed deformation-induced elastic softening. Let us also note that the development of tough, albeit elastically soft, titanium alloys is a highly topical research quest, see Section 2.3 for details.

3 Predicting the peculiar mechanical behavior of biocompatible Ti-Zr-Nb-Sn shape memory alloys via computational modeling

Superelasticity and shape memory effect are remarkable phenomena of so-called shape memory alloys (SMA), which are widely employed in the medical industry (archwires, catheters, stents, retractors, etc.). NiTi-based shape memory alloys are most established and widespread, although the serious health hazards of nickel have been recognized and documented [5]. This motivates the search for alternative SMAs that avoid the addition of nickel and other potentially medically unsafe elements.

Since shape memory phenomena are based on reversible martensitic transformations, metastable titanium alloys naturally come into focus. Delicate variations in chemical composition allow tuning of properties to meet the requirements of human-body applications. For instance, niobium is an efficient β -phase stabilizing element; the addition of tin reduces stress hysteresis and transformation temperatures and increases the recovery strain; the addition of zirconium can, under specific conditions, increase the recovery strain, etc. [1]. Hence, it is no wonder that the Ti-Zr-Nb-Sn system was identified as promising superelastic, hypoallergenic β -titanium alloys for biomedical tools and devices [6].

The cost-effective development and design of final products usually employs a computational model, whose core is a constitutive law of the material. The core must provide the relation between stress and strain (and temperature) to the computational engine (e.g., based on the finite element method), thereby solving the time evolution of the product subjected to (thermo)mechanical loading.

For proper formulation and parameterization of the constitutive core, extensive characterization of the mechanical behavior under simple loading scenarios is essential. A set of tensile tests at different temperatures (typical for SMA characterization) was conducted on the Ti-18Zr-11Nb-3Sn (wt.%) samples. Since the presumed activation of TWIP, the loading protocol consisted of loading up to 4% tensile strain, followed by 25 “training cycles”, in which the sample is repeatedly unloaded to 10 MPa and reloaded to 4% strain (w.r.t. the initial length).

Figure 2 presents the stress-strain dependence in the last cycle of the “training” performed at temperatures $-25\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $25\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $50\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. The increment of strain at unloading to 10 MPa in the last cycle with respect to the previous cycle was less than 0.02% in all cases, confirming the very good stability

Figure 2: The last cycle of tensile cycling tests of Ti-18Zr-11Nb-3Sn performed at different temperatures. Dashed lines denote the (idealized) purely elastic unloading path of the sample, which is used for the determination of transformation-related reversible strain indicated by ϵ^* .

of the mechanical response of the “trained” samples. Due to the Calusius-Claperon type of dependence between stress and temperature valid for martensitic transformation in SMA, the stress at “plateau-like” parts of the curves increases with increasing temperature. Capturing such an evolution and the shape of the hysteresis loop is essential for the constitutive model, see our previous works [7, 8].

To determine the (idealized) transformation-related reversible strain in a loading cycle, the dashed lines in Fig. 2 mark the (idealized) purely elastic unloading path of the material. Their intersections with the stress axis determine such reversible strain (labelled by ε^* for $-25\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$); it reaches almost 2% for $0\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and $25\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, just about 1.75% for $-25\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and less than 1.5% for $50\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. This shows that the alloy achieves its optimal superelastic performance at temperatures comfortable for the human body, which is beneficial for biomedical applications. The coupled influence of plasticity on phase transformation and vice versa poses a challenge for future constitutive model enhancement.

4 Assessing the mechanical performance of hip joint endoprosthesis from Ti-Nb-Zr-O alloys via computational simulations

Another attractive feature of metastable β -titanium alloys is the ability to reach low Young’s modulus by simple alloying. The crystal lattice of martensitically transforming materials is less stable near the transformation temperature, which typically leads to elastic softening. Hence, by tuning the chemical composition, both high strength and low elastic modulus can be reached [9]. These qualities, along with chemical stability and corrosion resistance, make some metastable β -Ti alloys well-suited for use in load-bearing biomedical implants.

The elastic modulus of biomedical implants should be as close as possible to that of human bones to enable more physiologic load transfer and to avoid the so-called stress shielding. Stress shielding occurs when the mechanical stress typically experienced by the bone with an implant is reduced, potentially weakening the bone. This is primarily governed by Wolff’s law, which states that mechanical stimuli regulate the dynamic remodeling of bone, resulting in changes in density and microarchitecture [10].

A computational structural model of a bone-implant system can significantly facilitate the development, design, and assessment of new implants. The computational simulations are used not only to evaluate implants’ endurance properties but also to reconstruct the mechanical stress and strain distributions within the system to identify and localize potential risk of stress shielding.

To evaluate the performance of a hip joint replacement made of a novel Ti-Nb-Zr-O alloy family with easily tunable elastic properties, we have constructed an idealized bone-implant model and performed a computational structural analysis by finite element method (FEM). The geometry of a stem of benchmark endoprosthesis (produced by Beznoska, Ltd. [11]) is shown in Fig. 3(a) together with the computational mesh of 26,705 quadratic tetragonal elements. It was embedded into a simplified model of a thighbone, constructed as a cylinder with one base perpendicular to the symmetry axis and the other tilted by 35° , see the cut of the model along the symmetry plane of the implant in Fig. 3(b). The green region representing the prosthesis is fixed within the blue one representing the bone. The latter was meshed into 172,556 quadratic tetragonal elements and assigned isotropic elastic properties corresponding to human bone tissue, i.e., Young’s modulus $E = 17\text{ GPa}$ and Poisson ratio of 0.3, i.e., the shear modulus $G \doteq 6.5\text{ GPa}$. The system is mechanically loaded by applying a force distributed over the top circular side of the stem taper with the direction indicated by a golden arrow; see ASTM standard [12]. The nodes on the right-hand side of the bone model were completely fixed in displacement; this is marked with a magenta segment. The elastic properties of the stem were varied to study the influence of the stem alloy on the distribution of stress and strain within the system.

The spark plasma sintering method enables the fabrication of bulk metastable Ti-Nb-Zr-O alloys with spatially controlled chemical composition [13], thereby also enabling spatial control of elastic properties. In our example, the elastic properties of the stem were set either corresponding to Ti-23Nb-7Zr-0.8O, $E = 91\text{ GPa}$, $G = 34\text{ GPa}$, or to Ti-32Nb-7Zr-0.5O, $E = 62\text{ GPa}$, $G = 22\text{ GPa}$, corresponding to the local maximum and minimum within the compositional range studied in [13]. Fig. 3(c) illustrates

Figure 3: Computational simulation of loading of hip joint endoprosthesis. (a) Reference geometry with a FEM mesh superimposed. (b) Bone-implant FEM model cut along the symmetry plane of the stem. Applied force marked with a golden arrow, the side with nodes with fixed displacements marked in magenta. (c) The distribution of von Mises equivalent stress within the symmetry cross-section of the stem for Ti-32Nb-7Zr-0.5O. Note the non-linear segmentation of the colorbar.

the results on the distribution of von Mises equivalent stress within the symmetry cross-section of the softer stem (made of Ti-32Nb-7Zr-0.5O). As expected, the highest stress concentration is located in the neck, with a difference of less than 2% relative to the maximum of the stiffer stem. From an endurance standpoint, the two materials are nearly equivalent. However, the difference between the maximum von Mises equivalent stress reached in the bone (at the contact edge with the stem, not presented in the figure) amounts to approx. 20%, which may be a significant variation when assessing stress shielding. The next step of the work will be to investigate microstrains within the stem, with spatially heterogeneous (and even anisotropic) elastic properties, as a potential input to models of bone remodeling.

5 Concluding remarks

The contribution summarizes recent progress in the theoretical and experimental investigation of the mechanical behavior of three metastable β -titanium systems and provides a broader context from

materials research. It illustrates the benefits of synergy between computational modeling and material development for functional design of applications and outlines directions for future research.

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